

IDENTIFICATION OF THE QUASI-STATIC BEHAVIOR OF A WOVEN COMPOSITE SENSITIVE TO THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS USING NUMERICAL HOMOGENIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Some thermoplastic matrices can strongly influence the behaviour of composites due to their sensitivity to the environmental conditions (temperature and/or hygrometry). When the technical specifications of a design require a validation of the structure behaviour in a wide range of temperature and/or hygrometry, the experiments for both quasi-static and dynamic loadings become expensive and cumbersome. That can greatly restrict the rapid designs of structural pieces, in particular if only main mechanical characteristics such as rupture strain/stress or energy to be dissipated have only to be found. In order to answer to this problem, the present paper is dealing with the identification of the quasi-static behaviour of such composite using a homogenization at two scales (one for the yarns and one for the composite): in this case, the experiments are reduced because they only concern the matrix. The first obtained results for ambient temperature and for two different level of hygrometry lead to promising answer to this problematic. These results also offer the important keys of research outlooks related to a better water distribution inside the composite and the consideration of non-perfect fibres/matrix or yarns/matrix interfaces.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to economic and ecological reasons, the use of thermoplastic matrices is becoming more common in the transport sector such as the automotive one due to the imposed lightening of vehicles. The integration of this type of material requires much more complex and comprehensive knowledge as well as robust numerical tools, especially for the pre-design phases.

For certain thermoplastic matrices, environmental conditions (temperature and/or hygrometry) play a predominant role in the mechanical response of composite structures [1]-[3]. Since the automotive specifications impose to validate the structure response over a wide range of temperature (from -40°C to $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$) and **Relative Humidity** (from dry climate – 0% RH to humid climate – 85% RH), the mechanical characterization of composites with thermoplastic matrices becomes very expensive and can be very long. For quasi-static experiments, it is usually necessary to carry out 5 tests (repeatability) by orientation (generally 0° , 45° or even 90°) for at least both 3 temperatures (-40°C , $+23^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$) and RH (RH0, RH50 and RH85). This represents 90 to 135 experimental trials to be done. If we now include dynamic experiments, at least 4 different strain rates are required which increases the number of experimental tests to 360 or 540. The time spent for desorption and ageing the materials cannot be also ignored because it can last a long time (months). These long and expensive characterization experiments obviously limit the possibilities to choose material(s) during a pre-design phase. From a numerical point of view, even if there are constitutive laws, which take into account elastic and irreversible deformations, various damages as well as the strain rate sensitivity [4], they do not consider the temperature and/or HR sensitivity. Then, it is necessary to identify their material parameters for each specific temperature/HR pair.

In this paper, we are answering to the problematic of long, expensive and even restrictive experiments with numerical homogenizations [5]. In this specific case, we decrease the duration and cost of the experiments since only the matrix is investigated (the number of tests goes back down to 45). The

objective is to identify the main mechanical characteristics of a Glass/PA66 twill composite which can be used for a constitutive law [4] or which can be helpful in the pre-design phase.

In a first part, we present the experimental results of the quasi-static characterization of PA66 matrix but also of the Glass/PA66 twill composite for different temperature and HR pairs. In a second part, we describe the adopted methodology to realize the numerical tool. It is split into two main parts: a first homogenization for a yarn and a second homogenization at the level of the **Representative Elementary Volume (REV)** of the composite material. Regarding the constitutive laws, we briefly introduce the specific constitutive laws dedicated to both thermoplastic matrix and yarns. In a last part, we offer some comparisons between quasi-static results resulting from the double-scale homogenization and the experimental results. Finally, we detail the outlooks that concern two main modelling assumptions: the perfect contact between fibres/matrix and yarns/matrix and the homogeneous distribution of moisture within the composite.

2 QUASI-STATIC EXPERIMENTS

2.1 PA66 matrix

The geometry of the test pieces used for quasi-static tests is standard one of flat specimens designed to be used with serrated grips. The dimensions of the zone of interest are $80 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ and the thickness is 4 mm . Since the tests include different levels of relative humidity, the specimens were first "dry" (RH0) using a vacuum drying chamber (BINDER VD-115 equipped with a Vaccubrand pumping unit PC 3001 VARIOpro) during around one week at $+90^\circ\text{C}$. Once the samples were at RH0, the ageing (RH50 and RH85) was done using a climatic chamber (BINDER KMF 115). The specimens stayed at $+70^\circ\text{C}$ during around 2 weeks, respectively at 50% and 70% level of humidity. Then, all the specimens were bagged using specific heat-sealed pouches, to protect them and to maintain their RH until the experiments were carried out.

The quasi-static tests were done on a standard tensile machine (INSTRON 5584) which was equipped or not (depending on the temperature test) with an INSTRON thermal chamber (temperature range from -150°C to $+600^\circ\text{C}$). The strain field were determined by digital image correlation using VIC software 2D and the stresses were obtained via the cell force of the tensile machine.

The figure (Fig. 1) depicts a summary of the quasi-static behaviour of PA66 for different temperature and hygrometry conditions. The observations show that stress-strain curves have a strong dependence on hygrometry, which imposes, at a given temperature, to the material a greater ductility more the HR is important. They also show a strong dependence on the test temperature since the latter determine the type of state (glassy or rubbery) as a function of the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the material. In conclusion, the temperature/RH pair affects all the mechanical characteristics of the matrix. As a result, this changeability of the matrix behaviour will influence, more or less, the behaviour of the composite material.

Figure 1: Quasi-static behaviour of PA66 for different temperature/RH pairs.

2.2 Glass/PA66 twill composite

The composite material studied is composed of four layers (thickness of around 0.5 mm) of a 2x2 twill glass and polyamide matrix 6.6 composite. The fibres volume fraction is approximately 50%. The geometry of the test specimens used for the quasi-static tests is a rectangular type test specimen whose dimensions of the zone of interest are 150 × 25 mm. The specimen width includes at least more than one and half the composite REV size, whatever the orientation of the composite (0°, ±45° or even ±30°). The conditioning procedure (desorption and absorption) is strictly identical to the one applied for the matrix. The test devices and means as well as the measuring are also identical; only the post-processing of the data must be adapted according to the tested orientation to extract the local stresses and strains (orthotropic frame).

The first main conclusion of the study in the longitudinal direction is that the behaviour of the composite is slightly affected by the environmental conditions. Indeed, since the fibres are insensitive to the external environmental conditions, all the curves are relatively close and correspond to a purely elastic fragile behaviour. However, this is no longer the case in the shear direction, since these tests involve the matrix much more. In figure (Fig. 2), between the two extreme curves, there is almost 50% difference about the rupture strain and almost 60% about the rupture stress. We also note that the elastic part is very different. This implies a variation of the shear moduli but also of the yield stresses and corresponding strains. Damage levels as well as rupture energy rates are also a function of environmental conditions.

Figure 2: Quasi-static shear tensile behaviour of the Glass/PA66 twill composite.

3 DOUBLE SCALE HOMOGENIZATION OF THE WOVEN COMPOSITE

3.1 Principles of the numerical tool

Figure 3: Principle of the two-scale homogenization.

Based on some works coming from the literature review [6]-[7], the behaviour of the woven composite can be found using a double scale homogenization (Fig. 3) made up of two steps:

- A first step corresponding to homogenization at the microscopic scale of the constituents (fibres and matrix). The result of this homogenization will give the behaviour of a yarn.
- A second step corresponding to a homogenization at the mesoscopic scale (yarns/matrix). The result will finally give the behaviour of the woven composite.

Concerning the REV of the first homogenization (yarn), we use an REV of a unidirectional composite. For the second homogenization, we develop a methodology in a CAD software to create the microstructure of the composite. The reasons for this choice are mainly inherent to some future sensitivity studies about some REV parameters (shape of yarn, angles...).

For the numerical simulations, two main assumptions have been considered:

- Without much information about the quality and behaviour of the fibre/matrix and yarn/matrix zones, the contact between both fibres and yarns with the matrix is assumed to be perfect.
- The moisture distribution inside both yarn and composite is considered homogeneous, i.e. we assume that for a composite aged to a given RH, this RH is identical in both matrix and yarns.

In order to obtain the yarn behaviour for a given temperature and RH, we used a UD composite ($18 \times 10 \times 5$ mm) RVE with fibre volume fraction of 70% (to correlate the fibre volume fraction of 50% of the woven composite). On this REV, the boundary conditions are periodic type leading to identify the yarn behaviour in any orthotropic directions. The constitutive law for fibres is elastic fragile and the material data are the ones usually found in literature. Concerning the matrix, we have developed a nonlinear isotropic law with damage. The material parameters are identified from the experimental characterization curves for any available temperature/RH pairs.

For the numerical simulations about the woven composite, the REV dimensions are approximately $15 \times 15 \times 0.5$ mm for warp and weft directions and about $10.6 \times 10.6 \times 0.5$ mm in the shear direction. Because of the large REV size and to better represent the experiment conditions, only the central node was totally blocked and only the external faces in the loading direction (Fig. 4) have an imposed displacement (the other faces are free). These imposed displacements are those resulting from the experimental tests. For the behaviour of yarns, we have developed an adapted constitutive law (presented in the following point) whose material parameters are identified from numerical simulations of yarn homogenization. For the matrix, we use the same constitutive law and the same parameters as in the yarn numerical simulation.

Figure 4: Boundary conditions and loads of woven composite REV (0° and 45°).

All calculations are performed with Abaqus/Explicit software. The meshes of the REVs are made up of approximately 5,500 C3D8R elements for the yarns, 350,000 C3D4 elements for the 0° composite and 515,000 C3D4 elements for the 45° composite.

3.2 Matrix constitutive law

All the developments are done in the framework of thermodynamic irreversible processes for which the thermal phenomena are neglected. The expression of the elastic strain energy of the damage material is given by:

$$W_e^d = \frac{1}{2}(1-d) \left(E^*(1-\nu)(\varepsilon_{11}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{22}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{33}^e{}^2) + 2E^*\nu(\varepsilon_{11}^e\varepsilon_{22}^e + \varepsilon_{11}^e\varepsilon_{33}^e + \varepsilon_{22}^e\varepsilon_{33}^e) \right. \\ \left. + 4G(\varepsilon_{12}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{13}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{23}^e{}^2) \right) \quad (1)$$

From (Eq. 1), the stress/strain relation (Eq.2) as well as the expression of the thermodynamic variable associated to the scalar damage variable (Eq. 3) can be both found.

$$\{\sigma_{ij}\} = (1-d)[C^0]\{X_{ij}\} \text{ with } X_{ij} = 2\varepsilon_{ij}^e \text{ if } i \neq j \text{ else } X_{ii} = \varepsilon_{ii}^e \quad (2)$$

$$Y = \frac{1}{2} \left(E^*(1-\nu)(\varepsilon_{11}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{22}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{33}^e{}^2) + 2E^*\nu(\varepsilon_{11}^e\varepsilon_{22}^e + \varepsilon_{11}^e\varepsilon_{33}^e + \varepsilon_{22}^e\varepsilon_{33}^e) \right. \\ \left. + 4G(\varepsilon_{12}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{13}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{23}^e{}^2) \right) \text{ with } E^* = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (3)$$

The evolution laws are considered to be such as in (Eq. 4) where \bar{Y}^R is the release energy rate at rupture. The form of the function f_D satisfies as much as possible the experimental observations. In our case, the function is a 5th polynomial function.

$$\begin{cases} d = f_D(\bar{Y}) \text{ if } \bar{Y} \leq \bar{Y}^R \text{ and with } \bar{Y}(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} (\bar{Y}(\tau)) \\ d = 1 \text{ is } \bar{Y} > \bar{Y}^R \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The damage/plasticity coupling is done using both effectives strain and stress. (Eq. 5) gives the form of the plastic criterion, where the yield function $R(p)$ is a power function.

$$f_p = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \tilde{\sigma}' : \tilde{\sigma}' - R(p) - R_0} \text{ with } \tilde{\sigma}' = \tilde{\sigma} - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\tilde{\sigma})\mathbf{I} \text{ and } R(p) = \beta p^m \quad (5)$$

The material parameters have been identified using “automated” sheets from a spreadsheet program for each temperature/RH pairs. The table (Tab. 1) summarizes the material parameters at ambient for both RH50 and RH85.

	+23°C/HR50	+23°C/HR85		+23°C/HR50	+23°C/HR85
E (MPa)	2531	930	a_1 ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}^{-1}$)	$3.003 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.363 \cdot 10^{-1}$
ν	0.43	0.46	a_2 ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}^{-2}$)	$-5.938 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.250 \cdot 10^{-2}$
R_0 (MPa)	31.2	14.4	a_3 ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}^{-3}$)	$5.814 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.647 \cdot 10^{-4}$
β (MPa)	2093	880	a_4 ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}^{-4}$)	$-2.029 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$-2.833 \cdot 10^{-5}$
m	0.871	0.710	a_5 ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}^{-5}$)	$-1.256 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.210 \cdot 10^{-7}$
			\bar{Y}^0 ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}$)	0.954	0.787
			\bar{Y}^R ($\sqrt{\text{MPa}}$)	10.420	16.785
			d_{max}	0.730	0.693

Table 1: Data for PA66 for two different temperature/RH pairs.

3.2 Yarn constitutive law

The theoretical framework is identical to the one considered for the matrix. The main difference, from previous matrix law, is that a scalar damage variable is defined in each any direction of the yarn. Assuming a transverse isotropic behaviour, it decreases the number of damage scalar variable to only 2: one for transverse direction and one for the shear direction. The expression of the elastic strain energy of the damage material is given by:

$$W_e^d = \frac{1}{2} (C_{11}^0 \varepsilon_{11}^e{}^2 + (1 - d_{22}) C_{22}^0 (\varepsilon_{22}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{33}^e{}^2) + 4(1 - d_{12}) G_{12}^0 (\varepsilon_{12}^e{}^2 + \varepsilon_{13}^e{}^2) + 4(1 - d_{22}) G_{23}^0 + 2C_{12}^0 \varepsilon_{11}^e \varepsilon_{22}^e + 2C_{12}^0 \varepsilon_{11}^e \varepsilon_{33}^e + 2C_{23}^0 \varepsilon_{22}^e \varepsilon_{33}^e) \quad (6)$$

From (Eq. 6), the stress/strain relation as well as the expression of the thermodynamic variable associated to the scalar damage variables (Eq. 7) can be both found.

$$Y = - \left. \frac{\partial W_e^d}{\partial d_{ij}} \right|_{\varepsilon_e} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} Y_{22} = \frac{1}{2} C_{22}^0 \varepsilon_{22}^e{}^2 ; Y_{33} = \frac{1}{2} C_{22}^0 \varepsilon_{33}^e{}^2 \\ Y_{12} = 2G_{12}^0 \varepsilon_{12}^e{}^2 ; Y_{13} = 2G_{12}^0 \varepsilon_{13}^e{}^2 ; Y_{23} = 2G_{23}^0 \varepsilon_{23}^e{}^2 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The evolution laws are considered to be such as in (Eq. 8) where \bar{Y}_{ij}^R is the release energy rate at rupture in the direction ij .

$$\begin{cases} d_{ij} = f_{d_{ij}}(\bar{Y}_{ij}) \text{ if } \bar{Y}_{ij} \leq \bar{Y}_{ij}^R \text{ and with } \bar{Y}_{ij}(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} (\bar{Y}_{ij}(\tau)) \text{ and } \bar{Y}_{ij}^2 = Y_{ij} \\ d_{ij} = 1 \text{ si } \bar{Y}_{ij} > \bar{Y}_{ij}^R \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The choice to uncoupled release energy rate allows to increase the flexibility to represent the yarn behaviour. The damage/plasticity coupling is done using both effectives strain and stress and considering that the irreversible strains are dominating in shear directions (12 and 13). For the other directions, we introduce a coupling factor a_{ij}^2 . (Eq. 9) gives the form of the plastic criterion, where the yield function $R(p)$ is a power function.

$$f_p = \sqrt{a_{22}^2 (\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^2 + \tilde{\sigma}_{33}^2) + \tilde{\sigma}_{12}^2 + \tilde{\sigma}_{13}^2 + a_{23}^2 \tilde{\sigma}_{23}^2} - R(p) - R_0 \text{ with } R(p) = \beta p^m \quad (9)$$

The material parameters have been identified also using “automated” sheets from a spreadsheet program for each temperature/RH pairs.

4 COMPARISONS BETWEEN NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Elastic properties

The first results we propose, concern the identification of the elastic properties of the woven composite at ambient and for three different RH (Tab. 2). The comparisons between obtained values in front of the experimental ones are satisfactory except may be for RH85. Indeed, one of the reason could be the assumption of homogeneous moisture distribution that is not valid at this particular environmental condition.

	Numerical values			Experimental values		
	<i>HR0</i>	<i>HR50</i>	<i>HR85</i>	<i>HR0</i>	<i>HR50</i>	<i>HR85</i>
$E_{11} = E_{22} (GPa)$	24.03	21.79	19.71	22.67	22.65	23.24
$E_{33} (GPa)$	9.21	5.93	2.84			
$G_{12} (GPa)$	3.370	2.872	1.666	3.416	2.800	1.987
$G_{13} = G_{23} (GPa)$	2.372	1.971	1.083			
ν_{12}	0.030	0.069	0.062	0.020	0.075	0.079
$\nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$	0.079	0.225	0.300			

Table 2: Comparison of the elastic properties at ambient for different RH.

4.2 Shear behaviour at ambient and for two different RH

The figures (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6) show the results of double-scale homogenization at ambient and both RH50 and RH85. We note that, although we have taken two strong assumptions concerning the contact

between fibres/matrix and yarns/matrix as well as the homogeneity of the moisture inside the composite, the developed numerical tool allows to satisfactory obtain main mechanical quantities. This can be helpful in case of pre-design, having a quick idea of the possibilities offered by the composite material. We also note that the correlation is better in the case of RH50 compared to the RH85. Indeed, an additional numerical simulation (green curve in Fig. 6) which mixes a yarn behaviour at RH50 and a matrix behaviour at RH85 demonstrates that it is imperative to take into account the inhomogeneity of the moisture distribution in the composite.

Figure 5: Comparisons of the shear behaviour of woven composite at +23°C / RH50.

Figure 6: Comparisons of the shear behaviour of woven composite at +23°C / RH85.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOKS

In order to reduce time and cost in design studies that are including composite materials sensitive to environmental conditions, we propose a numerical tool based on a double scale homogenization: the first for the yarns and the second for the composite itself. Using this tool, the experimental characterization of the matrix reduces not only the number of tests to be performed but also the time required for ageing the materials. By developing suitable constitutive laws for the matrix but also for the yarn, the first results obtained are encouraging, especially from a quantitative point of view. However, the assumption regarding the distribution of moisture in the composite should be first improved finding the better moisture repartition. To achieve this point, others numerical simulations for others pairs of temperature/RH will be done and will lead to concretely identify the real role of this assumption for this numerical tool. Another main important point that must be considered is the optimization of the behaviour of the zones between the fibres and yarns with the matrix. Indeed, the perfect contact greatly stiffens the behaviour of the composite or yarn. The introduction of cohesive elements or appropriate contact would provide a better behavioural description. We must not lose sight of the fact that it is necessary to have computational costs that are not prohibitive either compared to the time spent experimentally.

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